

Ionophoretic Technique in Study of Biologically Important Aluminium(III) and Thorium(IV) Binary Complexes with Penicillamine [Metal(M)–Penicillamine System]

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Paper electrophoresis has been applied to the study of metal complexes in solution and attempts have been made to determine the stability constants of complex species. The properties and chemical reactions of naturally occurring D-penicillamine have already been subjected to wide ranging investigation. The most important reactions are the processes involving participation of the mercapto group, and the main biochemical aspects have been reviewed¹. Great biological importance is attached to the study of metal-sulphur bonds formed in such processes, primarily in the non-haem iron proteins² and the blue copper proteins³. The significance of this amino acid is enhanced by fact that it displays independent therapeutic activity. Sorensen⁴ demonstrated the anti-inflammatory activity of copper-D-penicillamine.

A search of literature⁵ reveals some reports on complexes of penicillamine with different metal ions, but no report on Al^{III} / Th^{IV}-penicillamine system is available. Hence, attempts were made to find out best conditions for metal(M)-penicillamine complex formation. In addition, the stability constants of these complexes were determined. An electrophoretic method of determination of stability constant of these complexes is described.

Results and Discussion

Metal (M)-penicillamine binary system: The electrophoretic mobility of the metal spot against a pH gives a curve with a number of plateaus shown in Fig. 1. Every plateau indicates the formation of a certain complex species. A plateau is obviously an indication of a pH range, where speed is practically con-

Fig. 1. Mobility curve [Al^{III}/Th^{IV}-penicillamine] system; temp. = 35°, ionic strength = 0.1 M.

stant. The first one in the beginning corresponds to a region, where the metal ions are uncomplexed. The second plateau in each case with positive mobility indicates formation of 1 : 1 complexes of cationic nature with further increase of pH the mobility in the case of Al^{III} metal ion decreases giving rise to a third plateau in the negative region indicating formation of 1 : 2 metal complexes of anionic nature. While in the case of Th^{IV} ion the mobility remains constant with increase of pH, which indicates that only 1 : 1 complex is formed in the case of the Th^{IV}-penicillamine system. Chemical literature also assigns prominent chelating properties to unprotonated anionic species of penicillamine while ruling out any such property to the zwitterion⁶. In view of the above observation, the complexation of Al^{III} and Th^{IV} ion with penicillamine anions [L²⁻] may be represented as follows

The metal spot on the paper is thus a conglomeration of uncomplexed metal ions, 1 : 1 complex and 1 : 2 complex. For the spot moving under the influence of electric field, the overall mobility is given by equation,

$$U = \sum_n u_n f_n \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) is transformed to the following useful form on taking into consideration the different equilibria,

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1 K_1 [\text{L}^{2-}] + u_2 K_1 K_2 [\text{L}^{2-}]^2}{1 + K_1 [\text{L}^{2-}] + K_1 K_2 [\text{L}^{2-}]^2} \quad (5)$$

where u_0 , u_1 and u_2 are the mobilities of the uncomplexed metal ion, the 1 : 1 metal complex and the 1 : 2 metal complex respectively. Equation (5) has been used for calculating the stability constant of the complexes of metal ion with penicillamine. For calculating the first stability constant (K_1) the region between the first and the second plateaus is pertinent. The overall mobility (U) will be equal to the arithmetic mean of the mobilities of the uncomplexed metal ions u_0 , and that of the first complex u_1 , at a pH where $K_1 = 1/[\text{L}^{2-}]$. With the help of the dissociation constant values of penicillamine ($k_1 = 10^{1.90}$, $k_2 = 10^{7.95}$, $k_3 = 10^{10.55}$) (Fig. 2), the concentration of penicillamine anion is determined for the pH, from which K_1 can be calculated. The concentration of chelating amino acid (penicillamine) species $[\text{L}^{2-}]$ is calculated with the help of equation,

$$[\text{L}^{2-}] = \frac{[\text{L}_T]}{1 + \frac{[\text{H}]}{K_3} + \frac{[\text{H}]^2}{K_2 K_3} + \frac{[\text{H}]^3}{K_1 K_2 K_3}} \quad (6)$$

where, $[\text{L}_T]$ is the total concentration of ligand penicillamine. The stability constant K_2 of the second complex can be calculated by taking into consideration, the region between the second and third plateaus of the mobility curve.

Fig. 2. Mobility curve H^+ -penicillamine; temp. = 35° , ionic strength = $0.1 M$.

The stability constants of the ML and ML_2 complexes ($\log K$ values) of metal-penicillamine have been found to be (11.50, 15.06) and (13.61, -) for the Al^{III} and Th^{IV} complexes respectively, at $\mu = 0.1 M$ and 35° . It can be concluded from these studies that penicillamine may be used to reduce the levels of Al^{III} and Th^{IV} from living cells.

Experimental

The apparatus and procedure were the same as described earlier⁵. Solutions of Al^{III} and Th^{IV} perchlorates were prepared by first precipitating out the metal carbonates from $0.1 M$ solution of sulphates or nitrate of the metals with solution of sodium carbonate (AnalaR). The precipitate was washed with water and treated with calculated amount of perchloric acid. It was then boiled on a water-bath and filtered to get stock solution of metal perchlorate ($5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$). Metal perchlorate solutions of appropriate dilution were used for spotting the paper strips.

Metal spots were detected on the paper using aluminon solution (B.D.H.) for Al^{III} and 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN) (E. Merck) for Th^{IV} . A saturated aqueous solution (0.9 ml) of silver nitrate

was diluted with acetone to 20 ml. Glucose, as a black spot, was detected by spraying with this solution and then with 2% ethanolic sodium hydroxide.

The background electrolytes used in the study of binary complexes were 0.1 *M* perchloric acid and 1.0×10^{-2} *M* penicillamine. Stock solutions of 9.0 *M* perchloric acid, 2.0 *M* sodium hydroxide and 5.0 *M* penicillamine were prepared from AnalaR grade chemicals.

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